

Customer Satisfaction towards Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank in Thoothukudi District

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Abstract

The Tamilnad Mercantile Bank is a fastest growing private sector banks in India. The study is focused on various factors that determine the customers' satisfaction like employees' behavior, banking services, banking performance, infra- structure facility and other value added services. Analysis was made by using various tools like percentage Analysis. The result showed that there was a significant relationship between the variable of customer satisfaction and banking services of the TMBL in Thoothukudi district.

Keywords: customer satisfaction, banking services, Tamilnad Mercantile Bank Ltd.

Introduction

Tamilnad Mercantile Bank Limited (TMB) is a bank headquartered at Thoothukudi Tamil Nadu, India. The bank currently has 509 full branches throughout India. TMB was rated as the fastest growing Private Sector Bank in India. A bank may be defined as an institution that accepts deposits, makes loans, pays checks, and provides financial services. A bank is a financial intermediary for the safeguarding, transferring, exchanging, or lending of money. A primary role of banks is connecting those with funds, such as investors and depositors, to those seeking funds, such as individuals or businesses needing loans. A bank is the connection between customers that have capital deficits and customers with capital surpluses.

Review of literature

Abdul A R. (2014) evaluated the customers' satisfaction towards the banking services rendered by the SBI in Kanyakumari District. The author conducted a literature search on banking services of SBI interviewing of its 150 customers and thoroughly scrutinized how it caters to the banking needs of the inhabitants of Kanyakumari district. The study also focused on various factors that determine

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the customers' satisfaction like employees' behaviour, banking services, banking performance, infra- structure facility, loan oriented services and other value added services. Analysis was made by using various tools like percentage Analysis, Chi- Square Test and charts. The result showed that there is a significant relationship between the variable of customer satisfaction and banking services of the SBI and the customers have a medium level of satisfaction. The SBI could consider the researcher's suggestions in order to alleviate its reputation and customer satisfaction.

Objectives

- To study about the socio-economic conditions of the customers.
- To identify factor influencing customer satisfaction
- To find out the customer level of satisfaction.

Sample Design

The researcher has used random sampling method to select the sample respondents. Only 150 respondents were selected at random from among the customers in Thoothukudi.

Limitation of the Study

- The study is limited only to 150 respondents.
- The study is conducted only in Thoothukudi District.

Data Collection

The study is based on both primary data and secondary data. Primary source of data were collected from customers through structured interview schedule by way of personal interview. Secondary data were collected from books, journals and Websites.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Gender of the Respondent

Gender	No of Respondents	Percentage
Male	106	71
Female	44	29
Total	150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 71 % of the respondents are male 29 % of the respondents are female.

Table 2 Age wise classification by the Respondents

Age	No of Respondents	Percentage
Below 25 years	10	7
26 to 35 years	38	25
36 to 45 years	53	35
Above 46 years	49	33
Total	150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 7 % of the respondents come under the age group below 25 years, 25% of the respondents come under the age group 26-35 years, 35 % of the respondents come under the age group 36-45 years, 33 % of the respondents come under the age group above 46 years.

Table 3 Occupation status by the respondents

Occupation	No of respondents	Percentage
Business	38	25
Professional	25	17
Private employee	50	33
Government employee	15	10
Others	22	15
Total	150	100

Source: Primary data

It is inferred that 25 % of the respondents are business people, 17 % of the respondents are professional, 33 % of the respondents are private employee, 10 % of the respondents are government employee, 15 % of the respondents are doing other work.

Table 4 Type of Account by the Respondent

Type of Account	No of Respondents	Percentage
Current A/C	48	32
Saving A/C	80	53
Fixed Deposit	16	11
Recurring Deposit	6	4
Total	150	100

Source: primary data

This Table shows that 32% of the respondents are Current A/c holder, 53% of the respondents have Saving A/c holder, 11% of the respondents have Fixed deposit a/c, 4% of the respondents have recurring deposit a/c.

Table 5 Years of Dealing with TMBL

Year	No of Respondents	Percentage
Below 1 Year	22	14
1-3Years	28	19
3-5 years	36	24
Above 5 years	64	43
Total	150	100

Source: primary data

This Table shows that 14% of the respondents are using TMBL a/c in below 1 year, 19% of the respondents are using TMBL a/c in 1-3 years, 24% of the respondents are using TMBL a/c in 3-5 years, 43% of the respondents are using TMBL a/c in above 5 years.

Table 6 Most important Reason for choosing TMBL

Reason	No of Respondents	Percentage
The brand name of the Bank	18	12
The Excellent service provided by this bank	26	17
ATM services	38	25

Net Banking Facilities	21	14
Location advantage	33	22
Any other	14	10
Total	150	100

Source: primary data

This Table inferred that 12% of the respondents are choosing TMB for the reason of brand name of the bank, 17 % of the respondents are choosing TMB for the reason of excellent service, 25% of the respondents are choosing TMB for the reason of ATM services, 14% of the respondents are choosing TMB for the reason of net banking facilities, 22%of the respondents are choosing TMB for the reason of location advantage, 10% of the respondents are choosing TMB for the reason of any other.

Null hypothesis (H0)

There is no significant between the gender of the respondents and their level of satisfaction with regard to consumer satisfaction towards Tamilnad mercantile bank limited.

Table 7 The gender of the respondents and their level of satisfaction

Gender	Level of satisfaction			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Male	31	56	19	106
Female	11	28	5	44
Total	42	84	24	150

Source: Primary data

Chi-Square Tests			
Particulars	Value	Df	Sig.value
Chi-Square	13.5	8	15.57*

Findings

- Majority of the respondents are Male.
- Majority of the respondents belong to the age group of 36 to 45 years.
- Majority of the respondents are private Employee
- Majority of the respondents are saving a/c holders.
- There is no significant between the gender of the respondents and their level of satisfaction with regard to customer satisfaction towards Tamilnad mercantile bank limited.

Conclusion

The Customer satisfaction and banking services of the Tamilnad Mercantile Bank and the customers have highly satisfaction of bank Service. The customer is looking for better quality services which enhance the satisfaction. Customer satisfaction was examined with different dimensions which observed from the cheque clearness, individual attention by bank, and solving customer issue and etc.

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